

Correlation analysis in the study of oxidation kinetics of aromatic acetals with *N*-bromosuccinimide in acetonitrile medium

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Manuscript received 11 February 2010, revised 09 November 2010, accepted 16 November 2010

Abstract : An attempt has been made to correlate the rate constants of substituted acetals with the chemical shifts of the benzylic proton of the acetals ($\log k_2$ vs δ). This correlation is similar to that of which is obtained between σ vs δ . The benzylic proton chemical shift in acetals is found to be the characteristics of acetals. The benzylic proton does not couple with other protons and hence appears as a singlet, which would ensure effective correlation.

Keywords : Chemical shift, correlation analysis, acetals, *N*-bromosuccinimide.

Introduction

N-Bromosuccinimide (NBS) is a potent oxidizing agent and has been used in the oxidation of several organic compounds¹⁻¹². Acetals play a vital role in bio-organic research in exploring biological activities¹³ (antimalarial, antiviral etc.). The susceptibility of acetals to oxidation¹⁴ and rearrangement¹⁵ is reported earlier. The present work constitutes an investigation on the kinetics of oxidation of aromatic acetals by NBS with a view to correlate the rate constants with Hammett substituent constants. An attempt has been made to correlate the rate constants of substituted acetals with the chemical shifts of the benzylic proton of these acetals.

Correlation analysis has been extensively practiced in chemistry since the early 1930's after Hammett¹⁶ discovered that for a number of systems linear relationships apply between the logarithms of rate and equilibrium constants. Such analyses have also been applied to demonstrate that correlations exist between substituent effects and chemical shifts in nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy¹⁷, mainly involving ¹H or ¹⁹F nuclei. Several reviews of such treatments have been published¹⁸⁻²⁰ and the theories governing the shielding mechanisms and substituent effects have been reviewed by Gorenstein^{21,22}.

NMR shielding parameters provide an excellent method for investigating substituent effect because the measurement depends on a transition state, that does not change

the chemical character of a molecule. Effect of substituents on ¹⁷O NMR spectroscopy²³ chemical shifts for *p*-substituted benzoic acids, methyl benzoates, cinnamic acids and methyl cinnamates, polar substituent effects on the NMR chemical shifts by *N*-acylanilines²⁴ and related compounds and novel substituent effect on ⁷⁷Se NMR chemical shifts in naphthalene peri positions²⁵ have been reported earlier.

Although acceptable correlation of the *meta*- and *para*-proton shifts with Hammett constants are available, in general better correlations are achieved for protons located not on the ring itself, but at a position some distance away from the perturbing electronic influence²⁶. The benzylic proton chemical shift in acetals was found to be the characteristic of acetals. Chemical shift correlation of such uncoupled proton with substituent parameter has been reported²⁷.

Results and discussion

The kinetics is studied for the oxidation of series of *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzaldehyde di-*n*-butyl acetals by NBS at 313 and 323 K.

The log of relative rate constants correlate well with Hammett substituent constant σ , with the reaction constant values (ρ) of -1.376 and -1.420 at 313 and 323 K respectively (Table 1, Fig. 1). The importance of this correlation is made use in deducing the mechanism for

Table 1. Chemical shifts (δ ppm), Hammett substituent constants (σ) and rate constants (k_2) for *meta*- and *para*-substituted acetals

X-C ₆ H ₄ CH(OC ₄ H ₉) ₂	δ (ppm)	σ	$k_2 \times 10^4$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	k_X/k_H at 313 K	k_X/k_H at 323 K
X = H	5.50	0.00	31.26	1.00	1.00
X = <i>p</i> -OMe	5.46	-0.27	81.12	1.77	2.85
X = <i>p</i> -CH ₃	5.48	-0.17	44.99	1.14	1.44
X = <i>p</i> -Cl	5.53	0.23	24.26	0.66	0.78
X = <i>m</i> -OMe	5.43	0.12	17.78	0.46	0.57
X = <i>m</i> -Cl	5.46	0.37	8.11	0.20	0.26
X = <i>m</i> -NO ₂	5.60	0.71	3.30	0.09	0.11
X = <i>p</i> -NO ₂	5.60	0.78	2.26	0.06	0.07

Fig. 1. Hammett correlation : Plot of $\log k_X/k_H$ vs σ the Hammett substituent constant.

the kinetic study. The negative slope indicates that positively charged activated complex is developed during the

course of the reaction.

Chemical shift (δ) vs substituent constant (σ) correlation :

Linear free energy relationships have been used in the correlation of frequencies and intensities of absorption bands with substituent effects²⁸. NMR shielding parameters provide an excellent method for investigating substituent effects. It is shown²⁹ that beta, gamma and delta substituents have effects on ¹³C chemical shifts, which may be better understood by assuming that the upfield shifts caused by gauche gamma substituents are not due to non-bonded interactions introduced with the gamma group, but due to removal of hydrogen on the beta substituent. Correlation analysis of ³¹P NMR chemical shifts with substituent effects for *ortho*- and *para*-substituted phosphitylated phenols is reported³⁰. ¹³C NMR chemical shift-substituent effect correlations in *p*-substituted 5-benzylidenebarbituric acids and 2-benzylidene-1,3-indane diones have been studied³¹. In the present study, correlation of PMR chemical shift δ values of aldehydic proton of aromatic acetals with the substituent constant σ has been reported (Table 1, Fig. 2). The fact that the correlation exists provides evidence to the dependence of chemical shift of the benzylic proton on the nature of ring substituent.

Fig. 2. Plot of chemical shifts (δ ppm) of the benzylic proton in acetals vs σ the Hammett substituent constant.

The use of $\log k$ vs δ_c (C=O) correlations is presented³² as a practical method to evaluate rate coefficients, which gives explanation for the substituent dependence on reactivity. In the present study, it is found that the second order rate constants of NBS oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzaldehyde di-*n*-butyl acetals are well correlated with the chemical shifts of benzylic proton (Table 1, Fig. 3). The correlation obtained here is similar to that of which is obtained between substituent constant and chemical shift of benzylic proton. This proton does not couple with other protons and hence its signal appears as a singlet, which would ensure effective correlation. PMR spectra of acetals taken in neat phase alone have been considered in the present study, by which solvent effect on the chemical shift values has been avoided.

The data in Table 1 show that the benzylic proton in this series absorbs in the region δ 5.43–5.60 and that these shifts depend on the substituent. The fact that a correlation exists between benzyl proton resonances of the *meta*- and *para*-substituted acetals and the corresponding Hammett substituent constant provides an evi-

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log k_2$ vs chemical shifts (δ ppm) of the benzylic proton in acetals.

dence that at least to some extent the dependence of chemical shift of the benzylic proton on the nature of ring substituent. This is due to the inductive and resonance effects of the substituent.

Delineation of parallel straight lines :

From Fig. 2, it is known that σ values are more positive in *meta*-position than in *para*-position. The influence of a substituent in *meta*-position is mainly due to the inductive effect whereas in *para*-position it involves resonance effect. Delineation of parallel straight lines evidently conveys the existence of different orientation of electronic interactions of *meta*- and *para*-positions. From the chemical shift values, it is evident that the order of shielding of the benzylic proton by the *meta*-substituents is OMe > Cl and they appear to give the closest approach to the linear relation. A markable feature observed in the plot is the fall of the *meta*-nitro substituent from the straight line. This may be due to the polarization of the C–H bond via strong inductive effect on the benzylic carbon that in turn causes adverse shift to downfield.

Though chlorine is also an electron withdrawing group, it would exert certain degree of resonance effect at *para*-position. The low δ value compared to unsubstituted acetal is in accord with this fact.

Experimental

Acetals were prepared by the standard method^{33,34} and characterized by their IR and PMR spectral data. Refractive indices and boiling points of the acetals were compared with reported values. The PMR spectra were recorded in neat phase (chemical shift are in δ , ppm downfield from TMS as internal standard).

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